

Numerical assessment of the hydrogen combustion process in a rotary cement kiln

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Abstract:

The paper presents the results of numerical investigations of the combustion process in the rotary cement kiln. Two burner designs were used for modelling. First, the combustion process for the solid fuels burner currently used in the installation was analysed. The results showed that H₂ co-combustion improves the combustion process by moving the flame profile closer the baseline scenario (co-firing only the solid fuels). However, due to burner design constraints, the share of H₂ is limited since this burner has not been originally designed for hydrogen. Subsequently, a new burner head was proposed, which allows for 100% H₂ combustion in the existing rotary cement kiln while maintaining the thermal power of 75MW. The new burner head was analysed for non-premixed and premixed combustion of hydrogen with air. The global combustion chemical mechanism and the detailed chemical mechanism based on the flamelet generated manifold (FGM) were adopted for numerical studies.

High temperatures were achieved for non-premixed combustion, which generated high NO emissions. On the contrary, the premixing of H₂ with air improved burner performance, i.e. the temperature was reduced with a significant decrease in NO emissions, while maintaining the required heat transfer in the kiln.

The numerical tests and analyses carried out formulate the basis for further research on a burner dedicated to 100% H₂ combustion.

Keywords:

CFD modelling, combustion, hydrogen burner, cement kiln, kiln burner retrofitting, CO₂ emission reduction

1. Introduction

Increased government, industry and society awareness of the climate changes, caused by the anthropogenic emission of the greenhouse gasses, brought to attention by the number of the Assessments Reports, published over a couple of decades by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, e.g. latest one [1], led to initiatives, such as Paris Agreement [2], which aim at mitigating the effects of the greenhouse gasses emissions on the global temperature rise. This induced subsequently a wave of commitments from different industries, e.g. ceramic, steel, cement, aluminium, fertiliser, to adopt the targets and roadmaps to achieve the significant reduction of their environmental impact [3–12] strategies were developed in many countries [13–19] which can provide low emission hydrogen to be applied in the industrial processes in place of carbon intensive feedstock and fuels. Plans for developing technologies for producing renewable hydrogen are very ambitious, e.g. European Union's goals are to install at least 6 GW of renewable electrolyzers by 2024 and at least 40 GW of them by 2030 [20]. This, among others, could lead to significant low-emission hydrogen production cost decrease, in fact already in 2021 estimated renewable hydrogen production cost in the EU

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was between 3.3 and 6.5 €/kg or even 2.2-2.9 €/kg (in most favourable locations), comparing to 2.65 €/kg in 2021 from steam methane reforming [21]. This could establish the foundations for even more intensive changes in the industrial process heavily relying on the fossil fuels.

Hydrogen itself exhibits very distinctive characteristics such as much wider flammable limits, very high laminar flame velocity, and noticeably higher adiabatic flame temperature than methane [22], which may have both beneficial and undesired impact on combustion behaviour in burners. Many studies concentrated on investigation of the hydrogen content in fuel or hydrogen addition to the gaseous fuel mixture on the combustion behaviour, e.g. [23–28] and most recently the hydrogen co-firing with solid fossil and alternative fuels was investigated [29].

NO_x control strategies air-hydrogen combustion, such as lean combustion and exhaust gas recirculation (EGR), were numerically investigated by Wang et al. [30]. They found that, in the study conditions of the small combustion chamber, EGR has a more profound effect on the NO reduction than air dilution, while the optimal EGR ratio is 30% with 20% of water vapour fraction.

A MILD combustion of the hydrogen and air was studied numerically and experimentally by Mayrhofer et al. [31] and Ferrarotti et al. [32], proving that this method is also effective for decreasing NO emissions and improving combustion efficiency also for hydrogen flames.

The effects of air and fuel staging on combustion characteristics and emissions in micro gas turbine were investigated by numerical simulations by Liu et al. [33], who confirmed that those methods are also very effective for NO emission reduction in hydrogen flames.

Extensive study of steam-diluted H₂/O₂ combustion system, focusing on the combustion efficiency, was conducted by Tanneberger et al. [34], which showed that high steam dilution ratios enabled swirl-stabilisation of the flame, while the jet flame exhibits a much higher power density and exhaust temperature. Moreover, they concluded that swirl-stabilised hydrogen oxyfuel combustion is suitable for technical applications.

From the literature review one can conclude that a number of issues related to hydrogen firing have to be taken into account and addressed while designing the hydrogen burner for the cement rotary kiln, e.g. hydrogen flame adiabatic temperature (which can cause high temperatures and increased NO emissions), hydrogen laminar flame velocity (which impose risk of flashback and short flame), possibility to stabilise flame by swirl, and methods for NO reduction by air and fuel staging, EGR, and water vapour injection.

The present study aims to numerically investigate the possibility of replacing the current burned fuels (RDF and petcoke) in the rotary cement kiln by hydrogen, addressing flame temperature profiles and NO emissions. First the retrofitting of the existing burner was made and then the new burner design for 100% hydrogen firing was proposed and numerically tested. No such studies have been published in the literature so far, while some demonstration work of firing 100% of carbon neutral fuels, and up to 28%_{en} of hydrogen, in the cement kiln has been recently demonstrated [35].

2. Methodology

2.1 Description of the rotary cement kiln installation

Figure 1 presents the cement production installation located in Maceira, owned by SECIL Group, which rotary kiln is the subject of the study.

Figure 1 Rotary kiln for cement located in Maceira Liz (Portugal)

The working schedule in the cement plant is round the clock, the production scheduling is continuous, and the stopping periods are planned periodically for maintenance. The type of products manufactured in the cement plant of SECIL are clinker and cement, being the production rate of clinker 461,612 t/year and the production rate of cement 592,115 t/year.

Figure 2 presents schematically the clinker production process. The raw meal enters the 4-stage cyclone pre-heater, where it is heated by direct contact with countercurrent hot flue gases from fuel combustion. In the pre-heater, moisture and organic compounds are released or converted at a temperature of around 800°C. Tires are mainly used as fuels in the secondary burner for pre-heating and at 850 - 900°C the main part of the limestone is calcined releasing CO₂ by the reaction:

The partially calcined raw material enters the rotary kiln where it is further heated and partly melts as it travels through the kiln, while forming agglomerates of clinker nodules.

Figure 2 Illustrative drawing of the clinker production installation

One of the most important equipment in a cement plant is the rotary kiln (see **Figure 3**), where the main chemical reactions forming clinker occur. Rotary kiln is a steel tube positioned at an inclination between 3 and 4 degrees and rotates at a rate of about 1.3 to 3.5 rev/min. Normally, the kiln is 50 to 80 meters long and has a diameter between 3 and 7 meters - the length depends on production capacity and the extent of preheating. SECIL's Maceira kiln is 63.5 meters long, a diameter of 4 meters and an inclination of 3.5 degrees. The inside of the rotary kiln is lined with refractory material as the high temperatures in the kiln would otherwise destroy the tube. This lining protects the shell of the rotary kiln against softening and helps to prevent excessive heat loss.

The rotation of the kiln causes the clinker granules to gradually move downwards to the other end, where fuel is introduced through the burner pipe, producing a large concentric flame in the lower part of the cylindrical kiln. The flame may reach local temperatures around 2000°C and the fuel used in the burner is usually petcoke and RDFs (Refuse Derived Fuels consists of plastics, paper and textiles).

As material moves below the flame, it reaches its peak temperature at about 1450 – 1500°C, before falling from the kiln tube into the cooler, where it is rapidly cooled with air. The hot cooling air is subsequently used in the rotary kiln as secondary air, improving the energy efficiency.

The main objective in the SECIL's kiln retrofitting project is to reduce the GHG emissions resulting from clinker production, through the design of a new main burner for the rotary kiln, allowing it to admit a higher degree of alternative fuels, as opposed to their fossil-based counterparts.

Figure 3 Illustrative drawing of the rotary kiln

SECIL is targeted at reducing the use of petcoke by 5 - 20% and introducing a greater number of biobased fuels, RDFs, and even hydrogen in the main burner with a consequent reduction of GHG.

At present SECIL is interested in H₂ combustion in the rotary kiln. The use hydrogen during combustion of alternative fuels (with lower calorific values than petroleum coke), could contribute to the optimization of combustion process, leading to a reduction of specific heat consumption (kcal/kg clinker) and atmospheric emissions (NO and CO₂).

3. Numerical setup

In this work, the numerical simulations were performed to model gas-phase reacting turbulent incompressible flow using three-dimensional steady Reynolds Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) approach. The simulations were carried out using CFD software ANSYS Fluent. The numerical set up solved the governing equations for mass, momentum, energy and depending on the combustion model transport equations for species or mixture fraction, reaction progress variable and their variances. The equations are written as follows [35, 36,37]:

- mass conservation equation

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u}) = 0, \quad (1)$$

where ρ and \mathbf{u} are the mass density and flow velocity, respectively,

- momentum conservation equation

$$\frac{\partial \rho \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u} \mathbf{u}) = -\nabla p + \nabla \cdot T + \rho \mathbf{g}, \quad (2)$$

where p is pressure, T is the Reynolds stresses tensor modelled with the SST k- ω turbulence model,

- gas species conservation equation:

$$\frac{\partial \rho Y_i}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u} Y_i) = \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{1}{Le_i} \frac{\lambda}{c_p} \nabla Y_i \right) + \omega_i, \quad (3)$$

where Y_i is the mass fraction of the i -th species, ω_i is the source term of the i -th species,

- energy conservation equation:

$$\frac{\partial \rho h}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u} h) = \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{\lambda}{c_p} \nabla h + \sum_{i=1}^{i=g} h_i \left(\frac{1}{Le_i} - 1 \right) \frac{\lambda}{c_p} \nabla Y_i \right) + \omega_h, \quad (4)$$

where h is the gas enthalpy, ω_h is the energy source term, λ is the thermal conductivity, c_p is the specific heat, and $Le_i = \lambda / \rho D_i c_p$ with D_i the diffusion coefficient of species i .

In this work, two methods have been used to model the H₂ combustion process: 1) the global and 2) detailed chemical combustion mechanisms.

The global hydrogen combustion mechanism is described by the oxidation reaction of hydrogen as follows:

The rate of the reaction (1) is defined by the approach combining both the Arrhenius finite rate model (FR) and the eddy-dissipation model (ED) as follows:

$$r_i = \min(r_t, r_k) \quad (6)$$

where r_t is the turbulent mixing rate defined as [38]

$$r_t = A \frac{\rho}{M_F} \frac{\varepsilon}{k} \min \left(Y_F, \frac{Y_O}{\nu}, B \frac{\sum_P Y_P}{1 + \nu} \right) \quad (7)$$

where Y is the mass fraction of oxidizer O , fuel F or product P , $A = 4.0$ and $B = 0.50$ are empirical model parameters, ν is the stoichiometric oxygen to fuel mass ratio, and ε and k are turbulence parameters determined by a turbulence model adequate for the flow conditions.

The Arrhenius rate, r_k , of the k -th reaction is defined as [37, 39]:

$$r_k = A_k T^{n_k} e^{-E_k/(RT)} \prod_{i=1}^{i=g} C_{Y_i}^{n_{i,k}} \quad (8)$$

where A is the pre-exponential factor, n is the temperature exponent, E is the activation energy, C is molar concentration of the i -th Y species.

In the detailed hydrogen combustion mechanism, the flamelet generated manifold (FGM) [40] has been used with the GRI-Mech3.0 [41]. This model parameterizes the flamelet over the mixture fraction and reaction progress variable:

$$c = \sum_{i=1}^{i=g} \alpha_i Y_i \quad (9)$$

where α_i are weighting coefficients, defined as $\alpha_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} = Y_{\text{H}_2, \text{inlet}}$, $\alpha_{\text{HO}_2} = 10Y_{\text{H}_2, \text{inlet}}$, $\alpha_i = 0$ for other species.

The basic idea of FGM is that the transport equations for detailed chemistry are solved in 1D and its solution (species mass fractions, reaction source terms and thermodynamic properties) is stored as a function of the reaction progress variable. When the FGM method is used in 3D CFD simulations, the transport equation of the progress variable is solved additional to the flow equations and other quantities of interest are retrieved from a lookup table. The default FGM model implemented in Fluent was used in the calculations without taking into account the preferential diffusion effects that assume changes resulting from differences in diffusion coefficients of hydrogen and other gaseous components. The FGM technique taking into account the effects of the non-unity Lewis number is currently under development to include in further simulations.

The discrete ordinates method was used to solve the radiation transfer equation governing the radiation heat transfer. The emissivity of the gas mixture was described by the weighted-sum-of-gray-gases model (WSGGM) that takes into account the emission of only H₂O species without CO₂ in the flue gas.

A polyhedral mesh with a cell size of 1 mm was used, throughout the domain. The mesh was refined at the burner to improve the computation accuracy.

4. Results and discussion

4.1 The cement kiln burner retrofitted by H₂ co-firing

This section presents the results of numerical modelling of the H₂ combustion process with additional solid fuels in the rotary cement kiln burner. Attempts have been made to introduce the maximum possible amount of H₂ for the existing burner.

Figure 4 illustrates the multifuel burner's head that was utilized for the combustion testing. The burner is a 75 MW full-scale burner that is already placed in a rotary cement kiln owned by SECIL. The fundamental characteristics of this burner are that the combustion primary air is divided into three streams: central air (located in the centre of burner head), axial air and swirl air (located at the edge of the burner head). The secondary air is fed externally as surrounding air. Petcoke is provided through a ring channel, while RDF is fed through a cylindrical inlet.

In order to simulate the hydrogen co-combustion in the kiln, hydrogen was injected to the burner through the following ways: 1) through the central primary air channels, 2) together with RDF. Calculations showed that only about 6% of hydrogen could be introduced through the central air channels. The limitation to the introduction of larger amounts was the very high flow velocities obtained, reaching values above 400m/s.

On the other hand the limitation to the injection of H₂ through the existing RDF pipe was the resulting low velocity of the medium. Introducing H₂ through pipes intended for solid fuels (e.g. RDF, petcoke, biomass) may be associated with the risk of flashback of the H₂ flame due to low flow velocities.

Figure 4 The head of the industrial 75MW cement kiln burner

Table 1 presents the cement kiln cases analysed in the computations. The case 1 was the reference case since it represents the normal operating conditions in the cement kiln. Due to the technical reasons (maximum allowable RDF share in the burner), the co-combustion of petcoke with RDF is at 40/60% ratio.

In cases 2-5, due to the specific properties of RDF (high heterogeneity, high variation of lower calorific value and high variation of moisture content), it was decided to co-combust RDF in a configuration with hydrogen, which was intended to improve combustion conditions due to its highly reactivity. The 4 mixtures of hydrogen and RDF were used in computations, where the H₂ content was 5, 7.5, 10 and 16%_{en}, respectively named as case 2, case 3, case 4 and case 5. In cases 2, 3 and 4, hydrogen was fed through the existing RDF inlet, while in case 5, hydrogen was fed through both the RDF inlet and central air channels.

Table 1 The cement kiln cases analysed in the computations

case	petcoke flow, kg/s	RDF flow, kg/s	H ₂ flow, kg/s	RDF share, %	H ₂ share, %
1 (40% petcoke, 60% RDF*)	0.888	1.538	0.0	60	0
2 (5% H ₂ , 95%RDF*)	0.0	2.446	0.0312	95	5
3 (7.5% H ₂ , 92.5%RDF*)	0.0	2.381	0.0469	92.5	7.5
4 (10% H ₂ , 90%RDF*)	0.0	2.317	0.0625	90	10
5 (16% H ₂ , 84% RDF*)	0.0	2.1682	0.1000	84	16

* on energy basis

Figure 5 shows the temperature distribution along the kiln for cases 1-5. When analysing the reference case 1, the flame is somewhat lifted since the heat up, drying, devolatilization and ignition processes take some time. For the reference cases 1, the flame appears around 3.5m from the burner head. It can be observed that maximal flame temperature is around 2000K. The flame was directed towards the free surface of the clinker that has a positive impact on heat transfer from the flame to the clinker bed.

Due to high content of moisture, non-homogeneities, highly variable particle size distribution, RDF is not recommended to combust as a sole fuel in the rotary cement kiln. Therefore, it seems advantageous to feed a hydrogen to maintain a stable process. Four cases of the H₂/RDF co-firing, namely cases 2-5, were numerically examined to assess the effect of hydrogen on combustion process (see **Figure 5c-e**).

The addition of 5% of hydrogen (that thermally replaces the RDF) creates a small H₂ flame directly attached to the burner while the RDF flame is much further away from the burner (see **Figure 5b**). Increasing the share of H₂ creates a longer continuous flame, i.e. the H₂ flame forms a uniform structure with the RDF flame. However, it was found that in case of 10% H₂ (case 4) and 16% H₂ (case 5), there is a high peak of temperature (>2300K) which can impose the danger to the kiln walls. In the middle variant (case 3), with 7.5% H₂, it was found that the peak temperature was significantly lower than in previous tests (~2025K), which does not impose a danger to the infrastructure.

Moreover, for the 16% H₂ (case 5), unstable pulse combustion was observed, i.e. fluctuations of the temperature and velocity fields (**Figure 5e**). Thus, case 5 is not acceptable not only because of the hazard of kiln wall damage, but also because of the improper combustion process.

Calculations showed that the conversion of the currently working cement kiln burner to a pure hydrogen burner is not possible in a simple way. Due to the limitations described above, the preservation of the proper combustion conditions of kiln cement is obtained for a maximum of 10% H₂ on energy basis.

Figure 5 Temperature contours (K) in the cement kiln combustion for H₂ and RDF combustion

4.2 The hydrogen burner for the cement kiln

In order to achieve the complete replacement of the solid fuels with hydrogen, the concept of a 100% H₂ burner head was proposed. **Figure 6** illustrates a burner head for pure hydrogen combustion. The proposed burner head consists of 4 rings and circular holes arranged axially symmetrically between the rings. The numerical

assessment of H₂ combustion in new proposed burner included: 1) non-premixed combustion, in which pure H₂ was only fed to the burner through circular holes and primary air was fed through rings separately (**Figure 6a**), 2) premixed combustion, where H₂ and primary air were together fed as a mixture through both holes and rings (**Figure 6b**).

Figure 6 The head of the prototype pure H₂ 75MW cement kiln burner

Table 2 presents cases with 100% H₂ combustion analysed in the computations. In case 6, H₂ and air were supplied to the combustion chamber separately (non-premixed combustion). The total air was split into two streams: primary air fed through the rings and secondary air fed externally surrounding the burner. The amount of H₂ supplied corresponded to a thermal power of 75MW. The total air to the combustion chamber was 35.47kg/s and 49.8kg/s, giving 32.2% and 85.6% excess air.

Cases 7 and 8 represent premixed combustion and differ in the concentration of H₂ in the combustible mixture. In cases 7 and 8, the concentration of H₂ in the mixture was 39%v and 24.5%v, respectively, so that the heat power was maintained at 75MW.

Table 2 The cement kiln cases analysed in the computations

case	H ₂ flow, kg/s, (at 293K)	H ₂ mole fraction in the fuel mixture, %	primary air, kg/s (at 293K)	secondary air, kg/s (at 1173K)	velocity (holes), m/s	velocity (rings), m/s
6 (non-premixed)	0.6250	100	14.33	21.14	296	70.0
7 (premixed 39% H ₂)	0.6250	39.0	14.33	21.14	100	100
8 (premixed 24.5% H ₂)	0.6250	24.5	28.66	21.14	160	160

Figure 7 presents the contours of temperature, O₂ mole fraction and NO concentration for non-premixed combustion of H₂.

The gas combustion process differs significantly from the combustion of solid fuels, therefore in the case of non-premixed H₂ combustion, the flame is attached closer to the burner outlet, and the shape of the flame is regular and axisymmetric (**Figure 7a**). On the other hand, in case of solid fuel combustion in the rotary cement kiln, the combustion was intense almost in the entire volume of the kiln, and the flame was directed towards the free surface of the clinker. Nevertheless, the temperature values, obtained from the combustion of hydrogen and from the combustion of solid fuels, were similar at the outlet of the kiln, where the temperature was about 1500K. In the non-premixed combustion of H₂ (case 6), fuel was fed at high velocity of 296 m/s, which had a beneficial effect on eliminating the risk of flame flashback. Due to the high gas flame temperatures obtained, the amount of primary air fed to the burner was optimized. This attempt did not bring the desired results of lowering the process temperature, but it was observed that increasing the amount of primary air

resulted in better mixing of fuel with air and intensification of the combustion reaction in the immediate area behind the burner. Because temperature was locally high (2500K), the process of NO formation by the thermal mechanism was very intensive and the generated NO emission was high, i.e. locally 4000 ppm, and 2000 ppm at the kiln outlet.

In industrial applications, the reduction of the flame temperature and NO_x emission is achieved by, among others, H₂O injection into the flame, oxy-combustion with recirculation, flox combustion and others. In this work, however, we decided to analyse the combustion of H₂ using the lean premixed method (low H₂ concentration in the combustible mixture).

Figure 7 Selected numerical results for 100% H₂ combustion in the 75 MW cement kiln, case 6 (non-premixed combustion, H_{2,inlet}=100%v), u_{H₂,inlet}=296 m/s, u_{PA,inlet}=70m/s, u_{SA,inlet}=7.0 m/s

Figure 8 and **Figure 9** show the contours of temperature, O₂ mole fraction and NO concentration for premixed combustion of H₂.

In case 7 (premixed), the fuel-air mixture consisted of primary air (in the amount of 14.33 kg/s like in case 6 non-premixed) and H₂ (in the amount of 0.625 kg/s like in case 6 non-premixed), hence the resulting H₂ mole fraction in the mixture was 39%. The velocity of the combustible mixture was 100m/s in both holes and rings. The premixed combustion in the above-mentioned conditions (amounts of H₂ and primary air) did not reduce the temperature, which, as in the case 6 (non-premixed), was locally 2500K (**Figure 8a**). As a consequence, high NO emissions were also achieved, i.e. locally 4700 ppm, and 3000 ppm at the kiln outlet (**Figure 8c**).

For this reason, case 8 used a mixture that was leaner in H₂, in which the H₂ concentration was 24.5%v. The velocity of the combustible mixture was 160m/s on both holes and rings. As a result of H₂ dilution, a significant reduction in flame volume and combustion intensity were obtained. The maximum temperature was achieved as 2200K (**Figure 9a**) and lower by 300K compared to case 7. At the same time to the temperature reduction, the NO emission decreased to around 100 ppm at the kiln outlet (**Figure 9c**). The reason for such significant decrease in NO emissions in the case 8 can be explained by Zeldovich thermal NO mechanism. In all presented simulations, the thermal NO formation is the only mechanism dominating the process of NO emission. The reaction of Zeldovich mechanism:

is the rate-limiting reaction with high activation energy E=319MJ/mol. Thus, the thermal NO mechanism is important above 1800 K due to the high-temperature dependence of the reaction (10). So, the thermal NO

emission is exponentially governed by the gas temperature, residence time of the gas in the high-temperature regions, and excess air levels affecting oxygen availability.

Figure 8 Selected numerical results for pure H₂ combustion in the 75 MW cement kiln, case 7 (premixed combustion, H_{2,inlet}=39.0%v), u_{burner,inlet}=100 m/s, u_{SA,inlet}=7.0 m/s

Figure 9 Selected numerical results for pure H₂ combustion in the 75 MW cement kiln, case 8 (premixed combustion, H_{2,inlet}=24.5%v), u_{burner,inlet}=160 m/s, u_{SA,inlet}=7.0 m/s

5. Conclusion

At the moment, non-premixed combustion techniques are used for the majority of current hydrogen combustion. Nevertheless, non-premixed combustion will result in the combustion area getting excessively hot, which will release more nitrogen oxides because hydrogen has a high adiabatic combustion temperature. Thus, lean-premixed combustion technique could be a good solution, but it has certain drawbacks to overcome, including incomplete mixing of hydrogen, a tendency to flashback, and a vulnerability to blowout. For these reasons, the premixed burner should have an appropriate design to ensure safe use, i.e. the mixing of H₂ and air should take place over a short distance and as close to the burner outlet as possible. Simultaneously, the design of the burner should ensure high mixture velocities over the full range of burner loads (even at minimum load) to prevent flame flashback. Also, because of the high velocity of hydrogen combustion, the nozzle is at risk of being destroyed by the combustion process because the flame is burning too close to it. To accomplish reliable and stable hydrogen combustion under premixed lean burn conditions, a combustor's design must be rational.

The numerical assessment showed that H₂ can be burned in a controlled manner with low NO emissions. Control of the H₂ combustion temperature is possible, especially in the premixed combustion process.

The presented burner head is only a preliminary study. Further activities should include the design of the entire burner and the construction of a pilot scale facility for hydrogen combustion. It will be crucial to design the entire burner structure along with the fuel and air supply and the localisation of their mixing. Hydrogen combustion facility must take into account systems that ensure safe and trouble-free operation.

It seems that the proposed method of H₂ combustion modelling (flamelet generated manifold model) is appropriate but in the next step it needs to be calibrated based on experimental data from the pilot scale facility.

The above work creates the opportunity to numerically evaluate the possibility to use 100% of hydrogen in the cement kiln and formulate the basis for the planning of the experimental activities and physical tests of the hydrogen firing in the kiln burner in the further steps.

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